

Spectrophotometric Studies of Copper(II) and Palladium(II) with 3',5'-Dimethyl-2'-Hydroxy Azobenzene-4-Sulphonic Acid (DMHAS)

S. B. GHOLSE, O. P. SHARMA and R. B. KHARAT

Department of Chemistry, Nagpur University, Nagpur-440 010

Manuscript received 28 July 1977, revised 21 December 1977, accepted 17 May 1978

3', 5'-Dimethyl-2'-hydroxy-azobenzene-4-sulphonic acid (DMHAS) has been synthesized and characterised. Its pK has been determined by spectrophotometric and potentiometric methods. It forms 1 : 2 chelates with Pd(II) and Cu(II) and the metal ligand stability constants ($\log \beta_2$) as determined by Janssen's method are found to be 22.86 for Pd-DMHAS chelate and 13.82 for Cu-DMHAS chelate. The analytical applications of this reagent in the determination of Pd(II) and Cu(II) are studied.

A large amount of literature is available on the spectrophotometric studies of Pd(II) and Cu(II) Chelates.¹⁻⁴ However, since 3',5'-dimethyl-2'-hydroxy azobenzene-4-sulphonic acid (DMHAS) is newly synthesized, the systematic study of chelate of this dye with Pd(II) and Cu(II) has been undertaken for the first time. In continuation of our earlier work^{5,6} this paper deals with the synthesis of DMHAS and its complex formation studies with Pd(II) and Cu(II).

Experimental

Apparatus and Reagents : The dye (DMHAS) was synthesized by coupling diazotised sulphanilic acid with 2,4-dimethyl phenol in alkaline medium. The product was isolated as its barium salt and converted into sodium salt by treating it with a calculated amount of sodium sulphate. The sodium salt was recrystallized from aqueous ethanol. The free acid was recrystallized from 50% ethanol. The purity was checked by potentiometric titration. The equivalent weight of the free acid was found to be 306.0 against a theoretical value of 306.3 (Mol.wt. of DMHAS=306.3). The product was found to be homogeneous by TLC. (Found : C, 54.6 ; H, 4.3 ; N, 9.5 ; S, 10.8. $C_{14}H_{14}N_2SO_4$ requires C, 54.9 ; H, 4.6 ; N, 9.2, S, 10.7). Solution of the dye ($pH=7.0$, $\epsilon=18400$, $\lambda_{max}=336$ nm) was prepared by dissolving it in aqueous sodium hydroxide. All other chemicals used were of reagent grade. Palladium and copper perchlorate solutions were used.

Beckman DU-2 Spectrophotometer along with silica cells of 1-cm thickness was used for measuring the absorbances. Beckman H-2 pH meter with glass-calomel electrode system was used for pH measurements.

All experiments were performed at room temperature (30°). The pH of the solutions were adjusted with NaOH and HClO₄ solutions.

Results and Discussion

pK of the ligand : The dissociation of the ligand may be represented as :

The pK of this reagent has been determined by spectrophotometric method⁷ from the relation :

$$pK = pH + \log \frac{A_I - A}{A - A_M}$$

Where A_I and A_M are the absorbances of the ion and the molecule of the ligand and A that of a series of mixtures of ions and molecules. The pK value has been found to be 9.91. The $-SO_3H$ group present might be dissociating at lower pH value and thus not permitting its determination under the present conditions of study. Irving and Rossotti's method⁸, a modified form of Calving Bjerrum's^{9,10} pH titration technique has also been used to determine the pK of the ligand at an initial ionic strength of 0.04 which gave the value, 9.80.

Spectrophotometric Studies of complex formation : The method of Vosburgh and Cooper¹¹ indicated the existence of only one complex species in each case giving the maxima at 480 nm for Cu(II) and 470 nm for Pd(II) at pH 8.0 and 3.5 respectively. The chelate formation was instantaneous. The order of addition of reagent and the temperature (5-95°) have no effect on the absorbance values. Cu(II) and Pd(II) chelates were stable in the pH range 8.0-9.0 and 3.5-8.0 respectively for more than 120 hr.

Beers law and physical constants : Beer's law has been found to obey from 0.16 to 6.0 ppm for Cu(II) and from 0.45 to 10.0 ppm for Pd(II). The effective concentration range for accurate determination, deduced from Ringbom plot was found to be 0.9 to 5.2 ppm for Cu(II) and from 1.7 to 9.2 ppm for Pd(II). The Sandell's sensitivity ($\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$) and molar absorptivity of Cu(II) chelate were recorded to be 0.013 and 5400 respectively, while that of Pd(II) chelate, the values are 0.037 and 4160. The relative mean deviation in percent and standard deviation were determined to be 1.48 and 0.0054 for Cu(II) chelate, and 2.16 and 0.0063 for Pd(II) chelate respectively.

It was observed that the maximum intensity of the colour development takes place when the mixture contains greater than five fold excess of the reagent with respect to Cu(II) and Pd(II).

For studying effect of diverse ions difference of $\pm 2\%$ in absorbance value was arbitrarily taken as an interference. The ions which do not interfere at all concentrations in Cu-DMHAS system are Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} and Pd^{2+} , while Cr^{3+} , Fe^{2+} , Fe^{3+} , Zn^{2+} have been found to interfere seriously. In the determination of Pd(II), the ions which have been found not to interfere are Pt^{4+} , Rh^{3+} , Fe^{3+} , Fe^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , and Co^{2+} . However, Ag^+ , Hg^{2+} , Os^{8+} and Ru^{8+} interfere seriously.

The composition of the chelates was determined by the method of continuous variation¹², mole ratio¹³ and slope ratio¹⁴. The composition of Cu(II) chelate was also confirmed by potentiometric titrations. The results obtained are in good agreement with each other and show that Cu(II) as well as Pd(II) form 1 : 2 (metal : ligand) chelate.

Janssen's method¹⁵ with suitable modification^{6,16} has been used to determine the stability constant of 1 : 2 chelates. The values of $\log \beta$ for Cu(II) and Pd(II) chelates have been computed to be 13.82 and 22.86 respectively which are in accordance with Irving-Williams order¹⁷.

Structure of the chelate : The anionic nature of the Cu(II) and Pd(II) chelates was established by electrophoresis and ion exchange using resin Amberlite IR-45 (OH). The appearance of only one inflection in the potentiometric titration corresponding to the addition of 1 mole of base per mole of ligand indicates the complete neutralization of the sulphonic acid group. The phenolic proton of DMHAS cannot be titrated under the experimental conditions. In presence of 1 : 2 ratio of Cu(II) and DMHAS, the phenolic proton gets displaced due to complex formation and can be titrated giving a base : ligand ratio of 2. The formation of 1 : 2 complex was confirmed by potentiometric titration of the ligand in presence of Cu(II) at ligand : metal ratios of 3 and 4 also. The liberation of proton in Pd(II)-DMHAS system could not

be studied by this technique due to the hydrolysis of Pd(II) at higher pH.

Thus, the Cu(II) and Pd(II) chelates can be assigned tentative structure (I) which are similar to those suggested by earlier workers for analogous systems.^{6,16,18}

M=Cu(II) or Pd(II)
Structure I

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Prof. K. N. Munshi, Head, Chemistry Department, Nagpur University Nagpur for providing necessary facilities.

References

1. R. BELCHER and C. L. WILSON, "New Methods of Analytical Chemistry" Chapman and Hall Ltd; London, 1964.
2. H. A. FLASCHKA and A. J. BARNARD, "Chelates in Analytical Chemistry", Marcel Dekker Inc., New York, 1972.
3. E. B. SANDELL, "Colorimetric Determination of Traces of Metals", Interscience, New-York, 1959.
4. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longmans, London, 1973.
5. O. P. SHARMA and R. B. KHARAT, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, **52**, 174.
6. O. P. SHARMA and R. B. KHARAT, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1975, **13**, 848.
7. A. ALBERT and E. P. SERJEANT, "Ionization Constants of Acids and Bases" Methuen, London, 1962, p 29.
8. H. IRVING and H. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2904.
9. M. CALVIN and K. W. WILSON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, **67**, 2003.
10. J. BJERRUM, "Metal Amine Formation in Aqueous Solution" Hasse, Copenhagen, 1941, p 298.
11. W. C. VOSBURGH and E. R. COOPER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, **63**, 437.
12. P. JOB, *Ann. Chim.*, 1928, **9**, 113.
13. J. H. YOE and A. L. JONES, *Ind. Eng., Chem. (Anal. Ed.)*, 1944, **16**, 111.
14. A. E. HARVEY and D. L. MANNING, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 4488.
15. M. J. JANSSEN, *Rec. Trav. Chim.*, 1956, **75**, 1397.
16. H. L. MAHALAHA, M. K. DAVE and D. D. SHARMA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **45**, 413.
17. H. IRVING and R. J. P. WILLIAMS, *Nature*, 1948, **162**, 746.
18. R. W. STANLEY and G. E. CHENEY, *Talanta*, 1966, **13**, 1619.